

WAYS TO IMPROVE ADVERTISING ACTIVITY IN A PRODUCTION ENTERPRISE

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10357335>

Abstract. *In this article, the improvement and development of advertising activities in the enterprise, the sales promotion system, short-term measures to attract customers, the provision of cheap and high-quality services to the population based on quick services, and a certain type of sales service to attract customers to the enterprise based on the PR system introduced with is considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, advertising service, integration, product, brand, competition, market.*

Introduction. Due to the socio-economic reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan, the implementation of national programs clearly and carefully developed by the head of our state and our government, favorable conditions and opportunities created by our state for entrepreneurs, suitable incentives for investment and development in our country in all economic indicators. rates are being monitored.

Today, Samarkand region is one of the developed regions of our republic in the fields of industry, agriculture, trade, transport and service. A number of positive activities are being carried out in our province to ensure stable growth rates in all sectors of the economy, deepen reforms in the social sphere.

The company always pays serious attention to marketing. After all, being a wholesale company, he always deals with customers. This implies the continuous development of marketing communications. If we look at the state of organization of marketing activities in the activity of the enterprise, the enterprise uses market and product-oriented organizational structures of marketing in accordance with the 4 main organizational structures of the organization of marketing services. And its structure is as follows.

The organizational structure of marketing activities based on product production allows enterprises to better adapt to each of the market requirements: production of products with different production technologies, short life cycle and high innovation requirements.

A market-oriented organizational structure of a marketing service in an enterprise is a type of marketing management structure in which managers of individual markets are responsible for developing and implementing strategies and plans for marketing activities in specific markets. The market-oriented organizational structure of the marketing service is shown in the diagram below

The working status of marketing concepts and its availability were studied in the study of enterprise activity. In particular, the targeted use of the company's concept of sales and marketing attracted my attention. That is, while the enterprise is engaged in wholesale trade today, attention is being paid to further strengthening relations with customers, to fully satisfy its capabilities, and to activate the attitude of marketing specialists to their work. In addition, digital marketing concepts are also used to receive orders. Promotions and discounts are announced through social networks.

Methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Today, as a result of increased attention to marketing activities, the company developed a marketing plan, which was formulated as follows.

Selling manufactured products is also an important marketing event. In the process of sales, the range of products also expands. Every enterprise is required to have its own sales channels in the organization of product sales. As channels of trade, middlemen who own the commodity are involved in the delivery of the product from the producer to the consumer.

Since the products produced in the textile sector in our republic are considered the main consumer goods, improving the mechanism of promoting their trade will serve not only to fill the domestic consumer market, but also to speed up the production process.

1. One of the main directions of the economic reforms implemented in the trade of production products is to meet the needs of a large segment of the population for various consumer goods and other services at a high level and quality.

2. The trading system ensures that the product becomes a commodity, at the same time, the sales process is the main factor shaping the quality, appearance and consumer requirements of the produced product. This situation allows to coordinate the production process with modern market requirements.

The sales promotion system is based on short-term measures to attract customers, quick services. The PR system mainly serves to introduce the company to customers with a certain type of sales support. In marketing practice, the system of demand formation in the sale of products is aimed at long-term strategic goals, and the system of sales promotion is aimed at short-term strategic goals. Therefore, the use of both systems in relation to each other ensures the efficiency of the sales process. Advertising, which is considered the main element of the system of demand formation, plays an important role in increasing the volume of sales.

Table 1

Advertising means of the enterprise and ways of forming public opinion

Visiting papers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be of high quality and professionally made. - You must provide detailed contact information about your company in your native language, English or another foreign language. - All employees must have business cards prepared in a uniform style.
Brochures and catalogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be of high quality. - It should be short, informative and demonstrative.
Customer and number of customer testimonials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recommend your products and services with confidence - Your best and most loyal customers and clients, preferably by their senior management. - These comments should be included in your promotional brochures.
Articles in printed sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - You need to clearly define your company as a market leader. - Your brochures should be cited. - You should hang it in your office. - Should be sent to your authorized buyers and clients.
Video material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must be taken professionally. - Must be interesting, informative and easy to find. - It should show the best qualities of your goods and services.

	- Must have a short, clear and targeted advertising idea.
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In terms of content, it should have deep and rich information, its appearance should immediately stand out and attract attention. - Must be professionally prepared and regularly updated. - The possibility of electronic question-and-answer exchange should be available. - Should be able to order and purchase online if needed

In the conditions of competition, light industrial enterprises in the region rarely use marketing tools to study the trade market and attract customers, or rather, they do not need such processes. The reason is that the main product of spinning enterprises is raw material, because its buyers are clear. However, the market is already realizing that sewing and knitting enterprises need a very strong set of actions not only to enter the foreign market, but also to sell products in the domestic market. Therefore, special infrastructures supporting the market activity of enterprises have been formed in our country and their activities are being developed. The activities of direct marketing and event marketing are still unformed as a start-up. Therefore, we have developed proposals for direct and event marketing activities in leading international and domestic trade enterprises.

During my research, I got acquainted with the elements of direct marketing in the activities of several wholesale enterprises in Uzbekistan and made an offer to the enterprise. Today, the company fully implements its communication policy. The communication policy of the company is to implement measures for the promotion of goods in the market: conducting advertising campaigns, giving relevant benefits and discounts to intermediaries and consumers, motivating employees involved in product sales;

The marketing communications complex of the enterprise is inseparable from the development strategy of the information system marketing tools (for example, direct marketing, advertising) that facilitate the exchange of ideas (knowledge) about the enterprise's products, its reputation with existing and potential consumers or customers and that ensures its stability, public relations, etc.) is competition. competitive environment. Marketing requires the manager to integrate production and sales into a single process and to have the qualities of a competent planner. Marketing communication allows not only to identify hidden needs for a specific product or service and to promote and advertise them at the appropriate place and time, but also to conduct research and practical pricing, forecasting and financing, product distribution and combined control.

Thomas Gad is a practicing advertiser and brand policy scholar who studies the academic and practical aspects of brand policy about successful brands. Any theory of the brand must first propose a model, a structure of the brand, in simple terms, a set of shelves on which brands are placed.

Thus, Thomas Gad offers his collection of four shelves, which he calls dimensions, for greater stability. By the way, that's why this book is called "4D Branding". These 4 dimensions are called:

1. Functional dimension (related to the usefulness of the product or service associated with the brand).
2. Social dimension (refers to the ability to identify oneself with a certain social group).

3. Ethical dimension (perception of global or local responsibility). It embodies the ethical values shared by the brand and its consumers.

4. Mental dimension (the ability to support a person). Simply put, a brand provides a personalized consumer experience.

In social networks, we can try our hand at promoting the company's brand. The reason is that social networks play an incomparable role today. The company does not use any social media today. For this reason, I created personal profiles of the company on Instagram, Telegram, Facebook and YouTube networks and developed proposals for promoting and improving the brand. This enterprise is considered one of the leading production enterprises in the region. Great attention is paid to the construction of small and large buildings in the enterprise, and more attention is paid to the reduction of waste in the use of production products in the enterprise.

Historically and even now, production and manufacturing work is considered one of the leading sectors for the country. Indeed, the role of production in the development of social relations and meeting the needs of the population is incomparable. Regulation of the production sector by the state, based on the needs of the population, the state has its influence on the economic activity of the society through economic and social policy, legal, administrative, economic support and influence, in order to improve the social situation. reveals the secret. methods. need to understand.

In order to improve and develop trade activities in the enterprise, we believe that it is appropriate to implement the following tasks:

- creation of economic and legal access to cheap and high-quality services for the population;
- creation of mechanisms for the development of the process of integration and cooperation in the fields of production and other services;
- creation of an effective mechanism of state regulation of production and trade;
- activation and acceleration of activities of production organizations protecting consumer rights;
- improvement of logistics systems in enterprise activity;
- increase the quality of after-sales service and improve timely service;
- be active on social media and promote your brand.

REFERENCES

1. Kotler F. Marketing Management. Former press course. 2-e izd. / Per. English pod ed. SG Bojuk.- SPb.: Peter, 2006. - 464 p.:
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 15, 2017 "On measures to further develop non-state educational services" //, September 15, 2017 //From/LexUZ
3. Musaeva Sh.A., Usmonova DI Innovative marketing "TURON EDITION" 2021 study guide.
4. S Musayeva [WAYS OF DEMAND FORMATION AND SALES PROMOTION IN "GOLDEN OIL" LLC](#) Science and Innovation 1 (A5), 215-220
5. MSAzimovna [Development of innovative marketing strategies in agriculture](#) Web of Scientist: International Journal of Scientific Research 3 (02), 538-544

6. MSAzimovna, RNUlug'bekovna [Development conditions and modern trends of business tourism around the world](#) INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMICS 2 (2), 63-66
7. Kotler F. i dr. Basic marketing. - M.: LLC "ID Williams", 2013.
8. MSAzimovna [MAIN RESULTS OF LABOR PRODUCTIVITY OF BILLURI SITORA HOTEL EMPLOYEES LLC](#) Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research 11(1), 348-352
9. MSAzimovna [THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF MARKETING PRINCIPLES IN IMPROVING THE INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.](#) Science and Innovation 2 (1), 47-53
10. S Musayeva [ACTIVITY MECHANISMS OF LOGISTICS STRUCTURES](#) Science and Innovation 2 (A2), 196-202
11. S Musayeva [WAYS TO IMPROVE GOODS DISTRIBUTION POLICY IN FURNITURE MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES.](#) Science and Innovation 2 (A2), 152-156
12. S Musayeva [THE NEED TO EVALUATE ENTERPRISES UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN.](#) Science and Innovation 2 (A2), 35-40
13. MSAzimovna [Ways to improve the use of marketing information in the assessment of "Stekloplastik" LLC](#) American Journal of Economics and Business Management 5 (11), 338-343
14. MSAzimovna [Ways to increase the effectiveness of advertising activities and IT of trade organizations](#) Asian Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities 12(3), 93-97
15. Usmanov IA, Musayeva Sh.A. Characteristics of marketing activities in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer-Reviewed Journal ISSN #: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, JANUARY -2021 <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/79>
16. Usmanov IA Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing organization in the market of construction services. Service. Scientific journal. - Samarkand. 2021, issue 2 - pages 86-90.
17. Usmanov IA Learning to provide construction facilities with management personnel. ORANGE TECHNOLOGY INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | September 2021. Pages 31-33 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>
18. Usmanov IA, Jumanov Sh.N. Ways to improve quality control of construction and assembly works. Oriental Renaissance: An Innovative, Educational, Scientific Journal in the Natural and Social Sciences. ISSN 2181-1784. Volume 1, Issue 10. November 2021. – P. 651-658 <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-improve-quality-control-of-construction-and-installation-works>
19. Usmanov IA Boriev Construction industry development strategy in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation. International scientific and technical magazine. Real estate: economy, administration. Moscow, MGSU-№ 4 / 2021
20. Ilkhom Achilovich Usmanov, MARKETING ACTIVITY RESEARCH OF "S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK" LLC INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL "SCIENCE AND INNOVATION" VOLUME 1, ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
21. Musayeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Instructional manual Publishing-creative department of "STAR-SEL" LLC. Samarkand-2023